

STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT IN DEVELOPING EDUCATION QUALITY AT MADRASAH IBTIDAIYAH NEGERI 2 TANGERANG

JONED CEILENDRA SAKSANA ¹, VERA YULIA HARMAYANTHI ²,
LUTFI HARDIYANTO ³, ADJIE SAPTA ⁴ and MOCHAMMAD SUBAGIO, MM ⁵

¹ STIE Ganesha, Indonesia. Email: Saksana64@stieganessa.ac.id

^{2,3} STKIP Kusuma Negara, Indonesia.

Email: ²vera_yulia@stkipkusumanegara.ac.id, ³lutfi_h@stkipkusumanegara.ac.id

⁴ STIAMI Jakarta, Indonesia. Email: adjiesapta@yahoo.com

⁵ Dirgantara Marsekal Suryadarma University, Indonesia. Email: bagiolab83@yahoo.co.id

Abstract

The purpose of this research is to determine the strategic management implemented by Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri 2 Tangerang in developing the quality of education. The research method uses a qualitative approach that describes the findings. Data collection techniques include in-depth interviews with respondents, observation by observing objects that occur in the field, documentation studies in the form of archives, meeting notes, and books related to the research focus. Conclusions in terms of strategic planning for developing educational quality which is carried out through mechanisms and stages: SWOT analysis. Formulation of strategic goals. Strategic Planning. Strategic Synchronization and Transformation. Strategic implementation. Strategic Implementation. Conclusions in developing educational quality through Curriculum and learning planning. Implementation of work programs in the field of student affairs, work programs in the field of human resources, work programs in the field of facilities and infrastructure, and work programs in the field of administration and finance. Evaluation of strategies in developing the quality of education through monthly monitoring mechanisms and every semester evaluation of learning, development of educational facilities, and human resource development. Furthermore, analysis through approaches to educators and education personnel for continuous improvement, in the aspects of learning quality and improving the quality of human resources.

Keywords: Strategic Management, Developing, Quality of Education, Madrasah.

INTRODUCTION

Madrasah as Islamic educational institutions managed under the auspices of the Ministry of Religion must be able to always carry out Madrasah development. One effort that can be made in developing Madrasahs is to develop the quality of education Madrasah. So that Madrasahs can develop and be accepted by various levels of society and the output or graduates from Madrasahs can adapt to the demands of the times and can compete with other educational institutions.

Madrasah is one of the educational institutions with Islamic characteristics which is always in the process of realizing and maintaining the quality of education. Madrasah education is part of national education which has no small contribution to the development of national education or national education policy. Madrasahs have made a very significant contribution to the process of educating society and the nation, especially in the context of expanding access and equal distribution of education.

Madrasah as educational institutions with Islamic characteristics have a very prominent presence in this Republic. This institution occupies a strategic role in the education and teaching of the younger generation of Muslims in preparing themselves to carry out their important roles in society in the future. The success of Madrasahs in preparing students to face more complex future challenges, such as: producing graduates who will become leaders of the community, leaders of society, and leaders of the nation who will help determine the direction of the development of this nation, is determined by the readiness of its managers. On the other hand, the failure of Madrasahs to prepare students to face future challenges will produce graduates who are frustrated, marginalized, and become a burden on society. This means that amid the onslaught of globalization which offers competition, Madrasah managers are needed who can implement a management system that is relevant to the conditions of the times.

The existence of Madrasahs continues to this day along with national development and education. As part of the national education system managed by the Ministry of Religion, it also remains in its functional order to participate in educating the nation's children. This remains relevant to the current goals and ideals of national education. In Article 3 of Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning Systems

The technical reference for the National Education Standards is the Madrasah criteria regarding the education system in all jurisdictions of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, with a scope consisting of eight standards, namely: content standards, process standards, graduation competency standards, standards for educators and education personnel, facilities and infrastructure standards, standards management, financing standards, and education assessment standards. In managing education, Madrasahs need resources, including leaders, teaching staff, and education staff who have professional skills and high integrity to achieve quality education. Quality education is a common dream and goal. However, in reality, Madrasah education is currently not yet fully able to fulfill common desires and goals, in other words, the quality of Madrasah education is still lacking.

Framework of Thinking

According to David, J. Hunger., & Thomas, Weelen. (2003:2). Strategic management is a way to control an organization effectively and efficiently, to the forefront of implementation in achieving the goals and objectives concerned. When preparing a strategic plan for educational institutions, it must include: (a) Formulation of institutional vision, (b) Formulation of institutional mission, (c) Formulation of institutional goals, (d) Formulation of targets, (e) Formulation of policies, (f) Formulation of programs, (g) Formulation of activities.

Strategic management is a fundamental decision that will direct educational institutions to strategic achievements by the institution's vision and mission into the future. Strategic management is related to what the vision, mission, goals, objectives, and future achievements of the organization are and is related to how the organization can mobilize existing resources to achieve these goals.

Figure 1: Strategic Management Model

(Source: Kompasiana.com)

Strategic management is a fundamental decision that will direct educational institutions to strategic achievements by the institution's vision and mission into the future. Strategic management is related to what the vision, mission, goals, objectives, and future achievements of the organization are and is related to how the organization can mobilize existing resources to achieve these goals.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a qualitative approach. Qualitative research is research that aims to understand the phenomena experienced by research subjects, for example, behavior, perceptions, motivation, actions, and so on. Holistically and using descriptions in the form of words and language in special natural contexts and by utilizing various scientific methods

Data collection technique

In this research, Esterberg in Sugiyono (2018:27). The data collection techniques used are as follows:

- a. Observation is a systematic experience and recording of symptoms that appear on the research object. Nasution in Sugiyono stated that observation is the basis of all science. Scientists can only work based on data, namely facts about the real world obtained through observation.

- b. An interview is a communication between two people which includes someone who wants to obtain information from a source by asking questions with a specific purpose. Defines an interview or interview as An interview is a meeting of two people to exchange information and ideas through questions and answers, so that meaning can be constructed on a particular topic
- c. Documents are records of past events. Documents can be in the form of writing, images, or monumental works by someone. Documentation is a method of searching for data regarding things in the form of notes, books, transcripts, newspapers, inscriptions, magazines, meeting minutes, agendas, and photos of activities.

Data analysis

Data analysis is the process of compiling data in the form of interviews, observations, and documentation as well as other materials collected by researchers to find a pattern or model which will later be reported systemically. The data analysis technique used in this research is the theory of Miles, Huberman, and Saldana which applies four steps in analyzing data as shown in the following figure.

Figure 2: Interactive Analysis Techniques

(Source: Miles, Huberman. and Saldana)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SWOT Analysis of Strategic Management in Developing Education Quality at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri 2 Tangerang

The next step after the Madrasah's vision and mission are formulated, then a SWOT analysis is carried out. Here, careful and detailed environmental identification, observation, and analysis will be carried out for the success of the vision and mission to be achieved. So in this case, SWOT analysis is an effective strategic planning method used to evaluate Madrasah's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. This process is the determination of specific goals in identifying both internal and external problems to achieve the goals that have been formulated.

We try to make strategic planning for Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri 2 Tangerang as good as possible and as detailed as possible. Therefore, we are taking steps to depart from the plans we had before, in preparing strategic planning we take several priority scales that we take based on an analysis of the needs and potential of stakeholders because that way it will be easier for us to determine the program to achieve the vision, mission, and goals of the Madrasah. In other words, when planning a strategy, we first review the strategy we had before. We do it together with all stakeholders in the hope that we can correct each other if one of us is negligent, so we remind each other.

Analysis of the internal environment is carried out to identify the positive and negative potential that exists within Madrasah's internal environment. This is done as an identification to maximize the existing potential to achieve Madrasah's vision, mission, and goals. To explore the internal strengths and weaknesses of Madrasahs, researchers can explore data through observation by monitoring infrastructure, human resources, and teaching and learning processes.

Internal analysis is formulated from data and information as well as observations and documentation obtained directly. Therefore, it will be identified the strengths that exist in the Madrasah environment and the weaknesses that exist in the Madrasah environment to be used as a formula for developing the quality of education. Apart from analyzing internal factors, external factor analysis is also needed because in developing Madrasah programs, Madrasahs also collaborate with parties outside the Madrasah. Therefore, there is a need for external analysis to determine the opportunities and threats that arise.

EFAS 	IFAS	Strength (S) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Support from school committee leaders and school leaders 2. Availability of adequate computer facilities 3. Availability of LAN and Wi-Fi network facilities and internet 4. Availability of adequate human resources 	Weakness (W) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Absence of SOP (standard operational procedure) 2. Unavailability of software Academic Information System (AIS) 3. The absence of specialized human resources developers and technical implementers Academic Information System (AIS) 4. Academic data is still not organized and stored well
	Opportunities (O) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Advances in information technology and supporting technology 2. Cooperation and partnership with other professionals 3. Demands of stakeholders 4. The price of software and hardware more affordable 	SO Strategy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commitment to improve services by implementing an AIS for SMK Muhammadiyah 1 Banjarmasin • In collaboration with AIS software developers 	WO Strategy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop SOPs of data management and academic information and implement them in AIS • Work with AIS software developers and train staff for the use of AIS
Threat (T) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The number of schools that have used the Academic Information System (AIS) Based Website let alone the cities that progress rapidly 2. Government policy change 3. Employees who are vulnerable to move 4. Possibility of data damage 	ST Strategy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Choosing the right AIS and whose output can be processed with other software to anticipate the need for different information formats • Choosing AIS that the security level is high enough 	WT Strategy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate and select the right AIS and have a high level of security • Train the AIS management staff and guarantee it with a reasonable salary 	

Figure 3: SWOT Matrix Analysis of Madrasah Negeri 2 Tangerang

(Source: Research Gate)

Based on the research results and discussion of strategic management in developing the quality of education, several things can be concluded, namely as follows:

- a. Strategic planning in developing the quality of education at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri 2 Tangerang is carried out through a mechanism starting from stages: (1). Preparation of Madrasah vision, mission, and goals; and (2). SWOT analysis, as well as (3) Determining the objectives of the Madrasah, then the results of this analysis become a basis for the Madrasah to formulate long-term, medium-term, and short-term program objectives. Long-term programs are formulated every four years and the results are outlined in the Madrasah Strategic Plan. Meanwhile, the medium term is outlined in the Medium Term Work Plan, and short-term strategic programs are formulated once a year at the beginning of the school year and outlined in the Madrasah Annual Work Plan. In preparing both the Strategic Plan and RKTm, all Madrasah stakeholders take an active role in their respective duties. The formulation of this strategic planning is a fundamental thing for Madrasahs to do because it serves as a work reference or signpost for the Madrasah to achieve the Madrasah goals that have been formulated together; (4) formulation of superior strategies.
- b. Implementation of strategies in developing the quality of education at Madrasah 2 Tangerang includes; (1). Review of curriculum and learning where this is carried out by implementing the learning process through methods that are appropriate to student development. In reviewing this curriculum, two fundamental aspects are the focus of attention, namely the improvement and development aspects. This curriculum review was carried out by the Madrasah curriculum development team, starting from the stages of analysis, formulation, and examination and then continued with determination by the Madrasah head through control and development. This curriculum review process is carried out with the aim that the learning process in Madrasahs always changes in a better direction to achieve learning goals; (2). Work Program in the field of student affairs which includes accepting new students (PPDB), coaching students, and developing students' talents and Madrasahat through extracurricular activities; (3). Work programs in the fields of human resources and public relations are carried out continuously and simultaneously. as well as habits related to worship and morals. Empowerment of human resources (educators and educational staff) is carried out through Madrasah activities and workshops to increase professionalism. At Madrasah 2 Tangerang, human resource empowerment for both teaching and educational staff is carried out routinely once a year by presenting resource persons who are competent in their fields (Internal Madrasah HR Development). For teaching staff who have status as civil servants, in addition to Madrasah internal HR development, there is a separate schedule for HR development (the schedule is regulated by the ASN HR Development Information Analyst, Administration Subdivision of the Office of the Ministry of Religion, Tangerang Regency). Apart from that, teaching staff and educational staff are required to take part in se-Madrasah or workshop activities independently, the results of which are then disseminated to all fellow educators and educational staff. The results of HR development at Madrasah 2 Tangerang so far have not been optimal because not all teaching staff and education staff are willing to carry out HR development independently and are constrained by scheduling HR development for

- educators with civil servant status which is scheduled at the earliest once every four years (4) work program in the field of facilities and infrastructure, (5) work program in the field of administration, (6) work program in the field of finance.
- c. Evaluation of strategies for developing the quality of education at Madrasah 2 Tangerang. Especially in aspects of the quality of learning and the quality of human resources. (1) The results of the learning evaluation at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri 2 Tangerang show that there are still several teachers who do not have complete learning administration, and use less varied learning methods; (2) The results of the evaluation of the development of infrastructure facilities show that the planning mechanism for the procurement of infrastructure facilities is quite good but is still lacking in the aspect of maintaining facilities and infrastructure. (3) The results of the evaluation of human resource development show that there are several educators and education personnel who do not realize the importance of carrying out self-development independently, and are satisfied with what they have now so they have little desire to change for the better.

Formulation of Strategic Goals in Developing the Quality of Education at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri 2 Tangerang

The next step after the vision and mission have been formulated is to formulate the goals to be achieved as an elaboration or implementation of the mission. A goal is something that will be achieved in the short, medium, or long term. In general, goal setting is based on key success factors which are carried out after determining the vision and mission. Goals will direct the formulation of targets, achievement strategies, policies, programs, and activities in realizing the mission. Therefore, objectives must provide a strong basis for setting performance indicators.

The preparation targets for developing the quality of education at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri 2 Tangerang involve six areas which have their aims and targets or indicators of achievement, such as:

- a. Field of curriculum and learning
- b. Student affairs field
- c. In the field of human resources and public relations
- d. Facilities and infrastructure sector
- e. Field of administration
- f. Financial sector,
- g. Extracurricular field.

In all these areas, at the end of each semester, an evaluation is carried out on how the program has been planned and implemented during one semester, then at the beginning of the next semester, a follow-up will be carried out on the results of the program evaluation. Formulating Madrasah goals is also crucial after formulating the vision and mission. It's like someone going

on a journey but without a destination, the journey will be in vain. Likewise, an educational institution must have clear objectives for the sake of creating the existence of that educational institution.

Strategic Planning in Developing Education Quality at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri 2 Tangerang

The long-term planning of Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri 2 Tangerang uses an eight-year period, where the planned goals for eight years are listed in the Madrasah Strategic Plan. For medium-term planning, it is arranged in a four-year plan called the Medium Term Work Plan, and for short-term planning it is arranged in an annual plan called the Madrasah Annual Work Plan and there is further planning for the Madrasah Activity Plan and Budget.

Of all these plans, their preparation cannot be separated from the main guidelines, namely the vision and mission of the Madrasah. The steps for preparing these plans are as follows:

- a. Formation of a Madrasah Development Team, consisting of the Supervisor of Islamic Religious Education and the Madrasah Committee as the director, the Head of the Madrasah as the person in charge, and several members to ensure the Madrasah Self-Evaluation process runs smoothly.
- b. Implementation of Madrasah Self-Evaluation which is a way to foster a culture of continuous quality improvement in Madrasahs. The results of the Madrasah self-evaluation are used as a report to the Madrasah Education Section of the District Ministry of Religion regarding the Madrasah's achievements for further development.
- c. Based on the results of the Madrasah Self-Evaluation, the Madrasah prepares a Madrasah Work Plan which contains an overall strategic plan, with priorities for developing the quality of Madrasah education which are formulated, can be observed, and measured. Thus, the Madrasah Work Plan becomes a Madrasah performance document that includes aspects of planning, implementation, priority scale, time limits, and measures of success.

So it can be concluded that in formulating the objectives of this Madrasah, Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri 2 Tangerang uses Madrasah's vision and mission as its guidelines. Departing from this goal, a Madrasah Development Team was formed which carried out the task of carrying out Madrasah Self-Evaluation. Then the results of the Madrasah Self-Evaluation are used as a basis for preparing the Madrasah Work Plan which consists of the Madrasah Strategic Plan. Medium-Term Work Plan. Madrasah Annual Work Plan and Madrasah Activity Plan and Budget, and then the Madrasah Work Plan is ratified.

Synchronization and Strategic Transformation in Developing the Quality of Education at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri 2 Tangerang

Vision and mission are basic concepts of planning steps prepared and determined by the Madrasah which become a reference for the Madrasah in achieving the desired goals. The vision of Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri 2 Tangerang is to excel in achievement, based on faith and piety and to form individuals with good morals. If we examine the word superior which is the first word in the vision, it can be interpreted as the best, the best in terms of learning,

infrastructure, services, input, and output from Madrasah 2 Tangerang. The indicators that need to be met to achieve the goals of this vision are the implementation of learning according to the applicable curriculum and carried out creatively and innovatively. And also combined with various extracurricular activities that will support the development of students' talents and Madrasah. Furthermore, for the application of the values of faith and devotion, the Madrasah includes the habit of Morning Prayer, dhuha prayer in congregation, noon prayer in congregation, as well as tahini juz 'amma and other selected letters which have become a habit and routine for students every day.

In preparing the vision and mission, it is also necessary to pay attention to history, current preferences, market environment, resources, and competencies that differentiate one organization from another. To formulate a vision, it is necessary to pay attention to trend watching, namely the ability to observe trends in changes that will occur in the future. With this ability, we can detect the direction of change that will occur in the future and various hidden opportunities. The ability to be a trendwatcher requires high competence in the field of science and knowledge related to something observed with spiritual qualities. After observing trend watching, the next step is the ability to formulate a vision based on the results of observations of changing trends that will occur in the future. To be studied thoroughly, there is harmony between the vision and mission of the Madrasah which has been formulated and determined.

Implementation of Strategic Management in Developing Education Quality at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri 2 Tangerang

To improve the quality of student learning, Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri 2 Tangerang implements learning programs that are fun and require students to be active, such as learning using electronic media and also learning using educational games. Learning at Madrasah 2 Tangerang is not only focused on learning in the classroom but also learning outside the classroom. This curriculum and learning program is prepared at the beginning of each school year.

- a. Field of Curriculum and Learning Curriculum is a fundamental thing that must be considered when a Madrasah carries out the process of teaching and learning activities. Because the curriculum is a tool to achieve educational goals and at the same time a guide in implementing learning at all levels of education.
- b. Student Affairs is an important part of the educational process. Therefore, the student affairs sector must continue to be developed through various student affairs programs.
- c. Admission of new students is a very important thing and must be carried out periodically every year. Therefore, the Madrasah must prepare everything related to accepting new students, starting from the committee, the strategies used to the technical admissions selection. Madrasah 2 Tangerang to recruit new students is carried out by conducting outreach through various activities in kindergarten and also holding annual events such as coloring and drawing competitions, listing and memorizing short letters for kindergarten students.

- d. Student Development When the researcher made observations on December 10, 2021, the researcher found several students who brought contact books to be signed by their homeroom teacher at Madrasahta. Then the researcher tried to find out about the connecting book.
- e. Extracurricular Program The development of extracurricular areas is carried out to explore the full potential of students. Extracurricular activities carried out at Madrasah 2 Tangerang consist of various sports, such as football, volleyball, futsal, basketball, martial arts, qiran, drum band, dance, painting, choir, and calligraphy.

Human Resources and Public Relations Sector Human resource empowerment is a series of processes to increase or develop the potential and abilities of individuals and groups concerning institutional development goals.

- a. Academic Development of Educators Educators is one of the determining factors for the success of educational goals. Every year we always strive for academic development for all our employees, especially teaching staff. The academic development that we carry out is solely aimed at ensuring that the teaching staff we have are always able to keep up with the demands of the times.
- b. Increasing the Capacity of Educational Staff Apart from teaching staff, educational staff also play an important role in the success of Madrasah's goals. Teaching staff have an important role in determining the quality of learning, while educational staff, in this case what is meant is administrative staff, can support the achievement of learning goals through their respective fields.

Facilities and Infrastructure Sector: To achieve the vision, mission, and goals of the Madrasah, it is also necessary to pay attention to the facilities, means, and infrastructure that support learning activities. So the Madrasah is trying to complete the facilities and infrastructure to create effective learning. Based on the results of observations made by researchers, researchers found that the facilities and infrastructure owned by Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri 2 Tangerang were quite adequate. With adequate facilities, teaching and learning activities will be carried out comfortably. The facilities and infrastructure available at the Madrasah are as follows:

- a. Representative classrooms;
- b. Madrasa headroom;
- c. Teacher's room;
- d. Playground;
- e. Reading corners are located in each class and each strategic corner of the Madrasah
- f. School health
- g. Healthy canteen;
- h. Teacher and student parking;

- i. Toilet
- j. Sports equipment and drumband.
- k. Vehicle for pick-up and drop-off.

The field of administration also plays an important role in the success of an educational program. Through this administrative sector, Madrasah 2 Tangerang has a One Stop Integrated Service program. Through this program, it is hoped that all Madrasahistration services can be served well. The financial sector is a central and vital area. Because Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri 2 Tangerang is under the auspices of the Tangerang Regency Ministry of Religion Office, the salaries of educators and education staff are paid. The mechanism used in the financial sector is that the Madrasah treasurer details costs and allocations to the district ministry of religion office. Then for reporting, manual recording and reporting is carried out via the application.

Strategic Evaluation in Developing Education Quality at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri 2 Tangerang

- a. The learning supervision that I carry out is also included in the Madrasahistration of Learning. For ad-Madrasahistration of learning related to the RPP Syllabus, we Madrasahta usually collect it at the beginning of the semester, and for ad-Madrasahistration such as learning journals, we Madrasahta report it every Madrasahggu, while for performance reports (sieka) we Madrasahta report it every end of the month.
- b. Evaluation of Student Affairs Strategy For the evaluation of the student affairs sector in terms of accepting new students, an evaluation is carried out on the extent to which the committee for accepting new students has been successful. The results of this evaluation become a basis for determining strategies for accepting new students in the following year.
- c. Then it is reported in the form of a report on the results of an examination of the analysis of needs for facilities and infrastructure as well as an analysis of the feasibility of using the available facilities and infrastructure.
- d. Evaluation of Strategies in the Administration Sector Evaluations carried out in the administration sector are carried out every month. An evaluation is carried out regarding the orderliness and tidiness of Madrasah administration management, including in the administration sector, evaluations are always carried out by the Madrasah headmaster at the end of every month. We always check the archives of incoming and outgoing letters as well as all Madrasah registrations.
- e. Financial Strategy Evaluation, namely an evaluation in the financial sector carried out by the Madrasah head regarding financial reporting every month. The reporting was prepared by the treasurer of Madrasah 2 Tangerang in the form of manual reporting and also an application. I always record every transaction we make manually and input it into the application. Then I report the report to the head of the Madrasah at the end of every month. In this way, supervision of the financial sector becomes more effective.

Implementation of Routine Evaluation of the Learning Process Evaluation of student learning outcomes means the activity of assessing student learning processes and outcomes, both in the form of curricular activities and extracurricular activities. Learning outcomes assessment aims to see the learning progress of students or students in mastering the teaching material that has been studied by the goals that have been set. As one of the factors that is of concern in developing the quality of education, success in the learning process is one of the activities that needs to be evaluated regularly. Monitoring and evaluation are key elements in strategic planning. The evaluation process itself must focus on customers, in this case not only students but also stakeholders.

The preparation of activity reports is carried out by Madrasah 2 Tangerang for all activities carried out, both by the person in charge of the activity or the coordinator from the teachers and students. The purpose of preparing this report is to obtain information regarding the implementation of Madrasah activities that have been completed. Through this activity report, the Madrasah can see to what extent the activities that have been held are by the Madrasah's objectives. Through the activity report, it can also be seen whether the activity process is taking place according to plan or not.

Evaluation of Activity Results and Providing Feedback At the final evaluation stage which is carried out at the end of each activity implementation period or the end of the school year. In this evaluation meeting, all coordinators or people responsible for activities report the results of activities or programs for which they are responsible. The evaluation techniques used are adapted to the conditions of the Madrasah and the program being implemented. Each Madrasah certainly has advantages and disadvantages, but the technique chosen is the technique that is considered most appropriate based on various considerations.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussions related to strategic management in developing the quality of education at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri 2 Tangerang, several substantive things can be concluded as follows:

- a. Strategic planning in developing the quality of education at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri 2 Tangerang is carried out through a mechanism starting from stages: (a). Preparation of Madrasah vision, mission, and goals; and (b). SWOT analysis, as well as (c) Determining the objectives of the Madrasah, then the results of this analysis become a basis for the Madrasah to formulate long-term, medium-term, and short-term program objectives. Long-term programs are formulated every four years and the results are outlined in the Madrasah Strategic Plan. Meanwhile, the medium term is outlined in the Medium Term Work Plan, and short-term strategic programs are formulated once a year at the beginning of the school year and outlined in the Madrasah Annual Work Plan. In the preparation, all Madrasah stakeholders took an active role in their respective duties. The formulation of this strategic planning is a fundamental thing for Madrasahs to do because it serves as a work reference or signpost for the Madrasah to achieve the Madrasah goals that have been formulated together; (d) formulation of superior strategies.

- b. Implementation of strategies in developing the quality of education at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri 2 Tangerang includes; (a). Review of curriculum and learning where this is carried out by implementing the learning process through methods that are appropriate to student development. In reviewing this curriculum, two fundamental aspects are the focus of attention, namely the improvement and development aspects. This curriculum review is carried out by the Madrasah curriculum development team, starting from the stages of analysis, formulation, and examination then continuing with determination by the Madrasah head and control (development). This curriculum review process is carried out with the aim that the learning process in Madrasahs always changes in a better direction to achieve learning goals; (b). Work Program in the field of student affairs which includes accepting new students, coaching students, and developing students' talents and Madrasahat through extracurricular activities; (c). Work programs in the fields of human resources and public relations are carried out continuously and simultaneously. As well as habits related to worship and morals. Empowerment of human resources (educators and educational staff) is carried out through Madrasah activities and workshops to increase professionalism. At Madrasah 2 Tangerang, human resource empowerment for both teaching and educational staff is carried out routinely once a year by presenting resource persons who are competent in their fields (Internal Madrasah HR Development). For teaching staff who have status as civil servants, in addition to Madrasah internal HR development, there is a separate schedule for HR development (the schedule is regulated by the ASN HR Development Information Analyst, Administration Subdivision of the Office of the Ministry of Religion, Tangerang Regency). Apart from that, teaching staff and educational staff are required to take part in se-Madrasah or workshop activities independently, the results of which are then disseminated to all fellow educators and educational staff. The results of human resource development at Madrasah 2 Tangerang so far have not been optimal because not all teaching staff and education staff are willing to carry out human resource development independently and are constrained by scheduling HR development for educators with civil servant status which is scheduled at the earliest once every four years (d) work program in the field of facilities and infrastructure, (e) work program in the field of administration, (f) work program in the field of finance.
- c. Evaluation of strategies for developing the quality of education at Madrasah 2 Tangerang. (a). The results of the learning evaluation at Madrasah 2 Tangerang show that there are still several teachers who do not have a complete teaching and learning administration and use less varied learning methods. (b). The results of the evaluation of the development of infrastructure facilities show that the planning mechanism for the procurement of infrastructure facilities is quite good but is still lacking in the aspect of maintaining facilities and infrastructure. (c) The results of the evaluation of human resource development show that there are several educators and education personnel who do not realize the importance of carrying out self-development independently and are satisfied with what they have now so they have little desire to change for the better.

Suggestion

Based on the discussion and conclusions regarding strategies for improving the quality of education, suggestions can be made as follows:

- a. For the strategic planning aspect, it has been good to fulfill several planning stages, so it needs to be continually improved so that the analysis of weaknesses and strengths as well as opportunities and threats for the institution becomes even better so that better programs can be prepared.
- b. For the strategy implementation aspect, weaknesses were found related to the HR development aspect. Madrasahs should take preventive steps related to this, for example through outreach to raise awareness of the importance of upgrading professional knowledge and skills so as not to be left behind by the increasingly rapidly developing changes.
- c. For the strategy evaluation aspect, weaknesses were found: there was a lack or lack of involvement of external parties in the evaluation process, resulting in evaluation results that were less than objective. It would be better if the Madrasah tried to involve external parties to the Madrasah, for example.
- d. For education experts, the evaluation results will be more objective. In the internal evaluation, there is no special team responsible for quality development, so the quality development objectives are not yet well structured. It is hoped that Madrasahs will have a Madrasah Quality Management Team so that the flow of quality development in Madrasahs will be more focused.

Reference

- 1) Ahmad, Furqon Hidayat. 2018. "Management of Strategies for Improving the Quality of Education at SDN (State Elementary School) Kalisat 01 Jember Regency." UIN Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang.
- 2) Ali, Mohammad. 2020. "Muhammadiyah Kottabarat Solo College Strategy", Journal, 07 (August).
- 3) Amen, Moh. (2016). Implementation of Strategic Management for Junior High School Principals in Serang Regency. Tarbawi Journal. Volume 2 Number 02 July-December.
- 4) Barnawi, Arifin Muhammad. 2017. Theory and Practice Education Quality Assurance System. Yogyakarta: Ar-Ruzz Media.
- 5) Dita, Hadiani Fananta. 2018. Strategy Planning in Efforts to Improve the Quality of Graduates at MTsN Medan. UIN North Sumatra Medan.
- 6) David, J. Hunger., & Thomas, L. Wheelen., (2003). Strategic Management. Yogyakarta : Andi Offset.
- 7) Fathurrohman, Muhammad. (2015). Religious Culture in Improving the Quality of Education, Yogyakarta: Kalimedia.
- 8) Fitrah, Muh. (2017) The Role of School Principals in Improving the Quality of Education, Quality Assurance Journal. Volume 3 Issue 1. February.
- 9) Matthew B. Miles, A. Michael Huberman, Johnny Saldana., (2014). Qualitative Data Analysis. Google Books. Sage

- 10) Maanarah, Siti and Supramono. 2016. Strategy for Improving the Quality and Image of Public Elementary Schools in Ungaran Semarang. Satya Wacana Christian University.
- 11) May, Dawn of Revelation. 2018. Quality Improvement Management of State Vocational High School (SMK) Education Institutions 1 Purwokerto. IAIN Purwokerto.
- 12) Mekarisce, Arnild Augina. (2020). Data Validity Checking Techniques in Qualitative Research in the Field of Public Health. Public Health Scientific Journal. Volume 12 Issue 2.
- 13) Muspawi, Mohamad. (2020). Strategies for Becoming a Professional School Principal. Batanghari University Jambi Scientific Journal. July.
- 14) Ngalimun. 2017. Education Strategy. Yogyakarta: Parama Ilmu